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THE INFLUENCE OF ORGANIC-MINERAL CHEMICAL AMELIANTS ON THE ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION OF SOILED SOILS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the technology of preparation of ameliorative substances based on solid household waste and a 10% weak sulfuric acid solution and its application to agriculture, especially during the environmental rehabilitation of salinized and acidified soils. Experimental tests of the prepared reclamation substance at two rates (10 and 20 t/ha) were carried out, and 10 t/ha was accepted as the optimal rate for production. Field test experiments with the application of the optimal rate were investigated. On the basis of the conducted tests, it was determined that the melioration effect of saline and salinized soils with the use of prepared chemical meliorant is very effective compared to soils washed with ordinary water. Thus, during washing with 4000 m³/ha water rate by giving 10 tons per hectare, the degree of soil salinization increased from 2.15% in the upper 0-25 cm layer to 0.99% in the 25-50 cm layer. It is possible to reduce it to 0.99% in a layer, to 2.001% in a layer of 50-100 cm. When the washing rate is increased to 4000 m³/ha, the degree of salinization in the corresponding layers is 0.39; It decreased to 0.45 and 1.003%. The degree of salinization decreased slightly with the washing rate of 12000 m³/ha and was 0.19; It was around 0.23 and 0.47%. All the listed washing norms and soil stratification have been completely eliminated. The prepared chemical ameliorant is very economical, as it is made on the basis of waste. Since the raw materials and waste required for its preparation are in the territory of the republic, there is no obstacle for the preparation of chemical ameliorant in large quantities.

Keywords: Salinity, salinization, solid household waste, sulfuric acid, melioration, washing meliorant.

Introduction. Almost 50-60% of arable irrigated lands in the territory of Azerbaijan are lands exposed to salinization to one degree or another. About 30-40% of these lands are uncultivated lands. In order to ensure the food security of the territory of the republic, first of all, these lands should be made ecologically healthy, and their productivity should be increased.

While it is possible to wash the salinized soils, which are not very heavy due to their granulometric composition, with ordinary water, chemical reclamation measures must be implemented to improve the salinity of the soils exposed to salinization [1,2].

For this purpose, land plastering measures have been carried out in the territory of the republic since the 60s of the last century. However, since the ameliorative efficiency of the applied fertilizer is very low, the issue of ecological restoration of salinized and degraded soils in the territory of the republic has not been resolved until today. The issue of its solution has become urgent, it is one of the most important issues facing us today [3,5].

Purpose of work. It is the preparation of more efficient chemical meliorants for the ecological restoration of the salinized and degraded lands in the territory of the Republic and the development of technologies for their application to agriculture.

The issues at hand. It is to select and systematize raw materials and wastes suitable for the preparation of chemical meliorant in the territory of the Republic and study their physical-chemical, mechanical, and agronomic properties.

The object of the study. These are salinized and salinized soils spread in different regions of the republic.

Analysis and discussion.

Raw materials and materials used.

The amount of organic matter, total nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and hydrocarbons contained in BMT, which is used as the main raw material, is considered the main indicators of chemical properties.

The chemical composition of the waste is given in table 1.

Table 1.

Chemical composition of solid domestic waste, in %

Na ₂ O	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	K ₂ O	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	MnO	Cl ⁻	YTI
1.70	1.02	2.56	16.49	0.58	2.56	1.31	27.11	2.63	0.25	0.10	0.82	42.5

Another raw material used is sulfuric acid (GOST 2184-77) and late.

Table 2

Chemical composition of gypsum rocks extracted from different deposits, in %

Substances	Ganja bed		Bed of Khans	Jeyranchol field
	1st field	2nd field		
CaO	26.81	23.72	28.80	25.79
SiO ₂	15.6	21.39	9.40	17.51
Al ₂ O ₃	3.01	1.87	4.90	4.45
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.16	3.12	0.50	2.31
MgO	1.17	1.09	0.21	2.06
N ₂ O	0.88	0.43	—	—
Na ₂ O	0.61	0.39	1.25	—
P ₂ O ₅	11.34	—	—	—
SO ₃	35,67	29,24	38.21	34.28
H ₂ O	2.39	1.05	1.51	0.64

The technological scheme of the purchase of organic-mineral liquid fertilizer and meliorating substance based on solid household waste and 10% sulfuric acid.

The purchase of organic-mineral fertilizer was developed in industrial conditions based on the data obtained in laboratory tests [4].

The technological process is carried out in the following sequence: solid household waste (1) is sorted and crushed (2) and then fed to the reactor (3). At the same time, 10% sulfuric acid is added to the reactor from acid tank (4). The ratio of the liquid part to the solid part in the reactor should be kept within 1:3. The stirrer is turned on and the mass in the reactor is stirred at 60 rpm for 1 hour. It is mixed rapidly until it becomes a horra (picture 1).

Figure 1. Technological scheme for the preparation of chemical meliorant.

1-sorting area, 2-shredder, 3-reactor, 4-acid tank,
5-auger, 6-drying drum, 7-sieve, 8-liquid fertilizer tank.

After the mixing is completed, the slurry formed in the reactor is neutralized with milk of lime and the liquid part is separated from the solid part by feeding the screw to the clamp (5). The neutralized liquid fertilizer with a pH between 6.5÷7.0 is made fully suitable for use in agriculture and sent to the packaging department.

The composition of the prepared liquid fertilizer is as follows (%): organic substances 65-75; NO₃ 0.60-

0.65; P₂O₅ - 0.30-0.45; K₂O - 0.30 -0.45, CaSO₄ - 0.10-0.11.

The content of the ameliorative substance in solid form (%): organic substances 76-77; CaSO₄-21-22; NO₃ -0.11-0.13; P₂O₅ -0.09-0.11; K₂O -0.07-0.10, the rest is water.

Agricultural tests of received remedial substances:

Tests of organic-mineral ameliorant prepared on the basis of solid domestic waste and weak sulfuric acid

were conducted in the territory of Gumlag village, Agdash region.

The pH of the soil solution in the washed area was 8.1, and the amount of humus was 2.40%. The amount of gypsum insoluble in water is 1.366%, and the amount of calcium carbonate is 7.17%. The total amount of absorbed bases in the soil is 24.20 mg/eq., the amount of absorbed calcium cation is 67.36% of absorbed bases, magnesium cation is 24.69%, and absorbed sodium cation is 7.95%. The degree of soil salinization varies between 1,992-2,202% on the

profile. During washing, the quantity of chemical meliorants is 10 t/ha, and the washing rate is 4; 8 and 12 thousand m³/ha were accepted. The experimental results are given in table 1 and table 2.

As can be seen in the chemical analysis data, as a result of washing with a water rate of 4000 m³/ha, the degree of salinization in the top layer of the soil was reduced from the initial 2.15% to 0.99%, and with a washing rate of 8000 and 12000 m³/ha, the degree of salinization was reduced to 0, respectively. It was possible to lower it to 39 and 0.19%.

Table 3

Changes in the degree of salinization of soils during the washing experiment with different water rates in the territory of Gumlag village, Agdash region, mg.eq/% H₂SO₄

Options	Depth, sm	Washing rate, m ³ /ha	HCO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	total of anions	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	salt-of total	Dry residue
Washing with an organic-mineral complex ameliorative agent	0-25	Primary soil	0.012 0.20	0.173 4.86	1,385 28.86	33.92	0.185 9.26	0.229 19.06	0.129 5.60	2,113	2.15
		4000	0.013 0.22	0.019 0.54	0.667 13.90	14.66	0.273 13.66	0.012 1.00	-	0.984	0.99
		8000	0.013 0.22	0.007 0.20	0.250 5.20	5.62	0.100 5.13	0.006 0.49	-	0.376	0.39
		12000	0.015 0.24	-	0.116 2.41	2.65	0.047 2.35	0.004 0.30	-	0.181	0.19
	25-50	Primary soil	0.015 0.24	0.150 4.21	1,316 27,42	31.87	0.225 11,24	0.204 17.04	0.082 3.59	1,992	2.01
		4000	0.013 0.22	0.025 0.70	0.673 14.01	14.93	0.267 13,33	0.019 1.60	-	0.997	0.99
		8000	0.013 0.22	0.009 0.26	0.286 5.96	6.44	0.110 5.52	0.011 0.92	-	0.429	0.45
		12000	0.015 0.24	-	0.149 3.10	3.34	0.059 2.94	0.005 0.40	-	0.226	0.23
	50-100	Primary soil	0.016 0.26	0.190 5.34	1,430 29.80	35,40	0.247 12.36	0.231 19,26	0.088 3.78	2,202	2.23
		4000	0.015 0.24	0.173 4.86	1,268 26,41	31,51	0.360 18.00	0.136 11.37	0.049 2.14	2,001	2.06
		8000	0.016 0.26	0.084 2.36	0.630 13,12	15.74	0.234 11.72	0.049 4.02	-	1,013	1.03
		12000	0.017 0.28	0.027 0.76	0.284 5.91	6.95	0.094 4.71	0.027 2.24	-	0.449	0.47

With all three washing rates, the degree of salinization of the 25-50 cm soil layer increased from 2.01% to 0.99; to 0.45 and 0.23%, and the degree of salinization of the 50-100 cm soil layer from 2.23% to 2.06, respectively; It decreased to 1.03 and 0.47%. At this time, chlorine anion was the best washed among anions, and magnesium and sodium cation among cations (table 3).

The amount of harmful salts remaining in the soil after washing is 4 in the upper 0-25 cm layer; 8 and 12000 m³/ha washing norms, respectively 0.054; 0.027 and 0.018%, 0.087 in a layer of 25-50 cm; 0.052 and 0.024%, and 0.818 in the second half-meter layer; It was in the amount of 0.212 and 0.125% (table 4).

Table 4.

The amount of salts remaining in the soil during the washing experiment carried out with different water rates in the territory of Gumlag village, Agdash region, mg.eq/%

Variants	Depth, cm	Washing rate, m ³ /ha	Ca(HCO ₃) ₂	CaSO ₄	MgSO ₄	Na ₂ SO ₄	MgCl ₂	NaCl	Total of salts	Including	
										Harmful salts	In % of total
Washing with an organic-mineral complex ameliorative agent	0-25	Primary land	0.016	0.616	1,124	0.053	0.032	0.284	2,125	1,513	70,20
		4000	0.018	0.914	0.028	–	0.026	–	0.986	0.054	5.47
		8000	0.018	0.334	0.017	–	0.010	–	0.379	0.027	7,12
		12000	0.019	0.143	0.018	–	–	–	0.180	2.00	
	25-50	Primary land	0.019	0.748	0.985	–	0.030	0.210	1,992	1,225	61.50
		4000	0.018	0.892	0.054	–	0.033	–	0.997	0.087	8.73
		8000	0.018	0.360	0.040	–	0.012	–	0.430	0.052	12.09
		12000	0.019	0.184	0.024	–	–	–	0.227	0.024	10.57
	50-100	Primary land	0.021	0.823	1,062	–	0.074	0.221	2,201	1,357	61,65
		4000	0.019	1,167	0.539	–	0.154	0.125	2,004	0.818	40,82
		8000	0.021	0.779	0.100	–	0.112	–	1,012	0.212	20.94
		12000	0.023	0.301	0.089	–	0.039	–	0.449	0.125	27.83

Among the salts leached from the soil, NaCl and MgCl₂ salts prevail. Based on the data obtained from the research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Conclusion.

1. It is appropriate to use organic-mineral melioration materials prepared on the basis of solid household waste and 10% sulfate ink during the improvement of the soil of Agdash region.

2. The option of washing with the application of an organic-mineral meliorant has a high efficiency compared to the option of washing with ordinary water.

3. Application of chemical ameliorant allows reducing the rate of washing to 8000 m³/ha, and in some cases up to 8000 m³/ha.

4. The amount of harmful salts in the residual salts in the washing option with the application of chemical ameliorant is several times lower than in the washing option with ordinary water.

5. Since the prepared ameliorant contains organic residues, the humus formation process takes place in the soil for a long time and the fertility of the soil increases.

6. It is very cheap because it is made from waste.

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